

Addressing the Hubble Constant Discrepancy through the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis

Paper #1895

By Antonios Valamontes

tony@valamontes.com

Oct 18, 2024

This work is licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Revision 1.0 Oct 18, 2024

Abstract.....	3
1. Introduction.....	3
1.1 Background.....	3
1.2 The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis.....	3
1.3 Objective.....	4
2. Theoretical Framework.....	4
2.1 The Structure of DLSFH.....	4
2.1.1 Dodecahedral Symmetry and Quark Configuration.....	4
2.1.2 Unified Lagrangian Density.....	5
2.1.3 Dark Photon Interactions.....	9
2.2 Modified Gravitational Interactions.....	9
2.2.1 Einstein-Hilbert Action and Gravitational Modifications.....	10
2.2.2 Higher-Order Corrections to the Einstein-Hilbert Action.....	10
2.2.3 Modifications at Small Scales: Corrections to Newtonian Gravity.....	12
2.2.4 Gravitational Effects in the Early Universe.....	13
2.2.5 Resolving the Hubble Tension.....	14
2.3 Dark Energy and Dark Matter Interactions.....	14
2.3.1 Dark Energy and Its Equation of State.....	14
2.3.2 Dark Photons and the Dark Sector.....	15
2.3.3 Interaction Terms Between Dark Matter and Dark Energy.....	16
2.3.4 Implications for the Hubble Constant Discrepancy.....	17
2.3.5 Constraints on Dark Matter-Dark Energy Coupling.....	18
2.3.6 Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions and Modified Gravity.....	18
2.3.7 Dark Photons and the Interaction Strength.....	19
2.4 Bouncing Cosmological Models.....	19
2.4.1 Overview of Bouncing Cosmological Models.....	19
2.4.2 Modifications to the Friedmann Equations in Bouncing Models.....	20
2.4.3 The Role of the Scalar Field in the Bounce.....	21
2.4.4 Cyclic Universe Models and the Role of Extra Dimensions.....	22
2.4.5 Predictions for Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Data.....	23
2.4.6 Implications for the Hubble Constant Discrepancy.....	24
3. Methodology.....	24
3.1 Data Sources.....	24

3.2	Parameter Refinement.....	25
3.2.1	Parameter Refinement Using LHC Data.....	25
3.2.2	Parameter Refinement Using Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Detections.....	27
3.2.3	Bayesian Inference and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) Techniques.....	30
3.3	Computational Methods.....	31
3.3.1	Bayesian Inference.....	31
3.3.2	Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) Simulations.....	33
3.3.3	Combining Bayesian Inference and MCMC.....	35
4.	Results.....	36
4.1	Predictions from Early Universe Conditions.....	36
4.1.1	Modified Gravitational Interactions in the Early Universe.....	36
4.1.2	Dark Energy and Early Universe Expansion.....	38
4.1.3	Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Refinements.....	38
4.1.4	Predictions Aligned with CMB Data.....	39
4.2	Local Universe Predictions.....	40
4.2.1	Predictions of Higher Ω_m in the Local Universe.....	40
4.2.2	Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interaction Terms.....	41
4.2.3	Late-Time Acceleration and the Hubble Constant.....	42
4.2.4	Alignment with Local Observations.....	43
4.2.5	Resolving the Hubble Tension.....	43
4.2.6	Predicted Range for Local Ω_m in DLSFH.....	44
4.3	Resolution of the Hubble Tension.....	44
4.3.1	Nature of the Hubble Tension.....	45
4.3.2	Adjusting Gravitational Effects in DLSFH.....	45
4.3.3	New Physics: Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions.....	47
4.3.4	Dynamic Equation of State for Dark Energy.....	47
4.3.5	Bridging the Gap Between Early and Local Measurements.....	48
4.3.6	Predicted Range for Ω_m in DLSFH.....	49
5.	Discussion.....	49
5.1	Implications for Cosmology.....	49
5.1.1	Re-Evaluation of Gravitational Theories.....	50
5.1.2	Redefining Dark Energy's Role in Cosmic Expansion.....	51
5.1.3	Testing and Empirical Verification.....	51
5.1.4	Paradigm Shift in Cosmology.....	52

5.2 Future Applications and Experiments.....	53
5.2.1 Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Detectors.....	53
5.2.2 Dark Photon Searches at the LHC.....	55
5.2.3 Superluminal Dark Photon Detection at CERN.....	56
5.2.4 Large-Scale Structure Surveys.....	57
5.2.5 Other Potential Applications.....	58
6. Conclusion.....	58
6.1 Resolving the Hubble Tension.....	58
6.2 Implications for Cosmology and Physics.....	59
6.3 Path Forward: Future Experiments and Testing.....	60
6.4 Broader Theoretical and Experimental Impact.....	61
References.....	63

Abstract

The Hubble constant discrepancy, a conflict between two independent methods of measuring the universe's expansion rate, poses a challenge to the current cosmological model. The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) integrates string theory, loop quantum gravity, and modified gravitational interactions to offer a possible solution to this discrepancy. By adjusting gravitational effects, coupling constants for dark energy, and incorporating data from bouncing cosmological models, DLSFH refines predictions related to the universe's expansion. This paper demonstrates how DLSFH's refined parameters could bridge the gap between early universe predictions and current observations, offering a new perspective on the Hubble constant tension.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The Hubble constant discrepancy has emerged as a critical issue in modern cosmology. Measurements of the Hubble constant (H_0) derived from the cosmic microwave background (CMB) and the local universe yield different values [2]. While the CMB-based method suggests a value of 67.4 ± 0.5 km/s/Mpc [2], local measurements using supernovae and other techniques indicate a value of around 74.0 ± 1.4 km/s/Mpc [9]. This disagreement, known as the "Hubble tension," suggests that either new physics beyond the standard cosmological model is required or that measurement techniques must be refined [13].

1.2 The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) is a unified field theory that combines string theory, quantum field theory, and general relativity. By utilizing dodecahedral symmetry, DLSFH creates a framework for understanding particle interactions and cosmological evolution in the early universe [8]. This model includes

modifications to gravitational forces at small scales, interactions between dark matter and dark energy, and the integration of gravitational-wave background (GWB) predictions from bouncing cosmological models [14][16].

1.3 Objective

This paper aims to apply the DLSFH framework to address the Hubble constant discrepancy, exploring how modified gravitational interactions, dark photon coupling constants, and GWB data can resolve the tension between early universe predictions and current observations [1], [7], [9].

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 The Structure of DLSFH

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) is built on a geometrical foundation of **dodecahedral symmetry**, which governs the organization of string qubits in the theory. Each quark is represented by specific configurations of 12 string qubits distributed across the 20 vertices of a dodecahedron, interacting along 30 edges. This dodecahedral structure ensures the preservation of symmetry, stability, and charge balance within particle configurations [8]. Below, we detail the mathematical formulation of each critical component of the hypothesis.

2.1.1 Dodecahedral Symmetry and Quark Configuration

The dodecahedron is a Platonic solid with 12 faces, 20 vertices, and 30 edges. The vertices are the interaction points where string qubits reside. These qubits are represented by the charge configuration of quarks, where each vertex corresponds to a quark interaction site. The symmetry group for the dodecahedron is denoted by **Ih**, which includes 60 rotational symmetries [8]:

- 12 rotations around fivefold axes (72-degree rotations),
- 20 rotations around threefold axes (120-degree rotations),

- 15 rotations around twofold axes (180-degree rotations).

These symmetry operations maintain the overall dodecahedral structure and ensure that the interactions between quarks, represented by string qubits, are invariant under symmetry transformations [8].

2.1.2 Unified Lagrangian Density

The unified **Lagrangian density** in the DLSFH encapsulates the gravitational interactions, gauge fields, fermion fields, Higgs fields, and string dynamics. It is expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{EH}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Gauge}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Fermion}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Higgs}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{String}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Dark Photons}} \tag{1}$$

Where each term represents a distinct physical interaction:

- **Einstein-Hilbert Action:** Governs gravitational interactions.
- **Gauge Fields:** Describe electromagnetism, weak nuclear forces, and strong nuclear forces.
- **Fermion Fields:** Represent quarks and leptons in the standard model.
- **Higgs Field:** Explains the mass generation through spontaneous symmetry breaking.
- **String Dynamics:** Ensures consistency with string theory.
- **Dark Photon Interactions:** Incorporates dark matter contributions.

Einstein-Hilbert Action for Gravitational Interactions

The Einstein-Hilbert action is the standard formulation of general relativity, and in DLSFH, it governs the gravitational interactions between string qubits. It is expressed as:

$$S_{\text{EH}} = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \frac{1}{16\pi G} R \quad (2)$$

Where:

- R is the Ricci scalar describing the curvature of spacetime,
- g is the determinant of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$,
- G is Newton's gravitational constant.

This term ensures that DLSFH incorporates gravitational interactions consistent with general relativity at low energy scales.

Gauge Fields for Electromagnetic, Weak, and Strong Forces

Gauge fields are responsible for mediating the fundamental forces. In DLSFH, the gauge fields from the standard model are represented as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Gauge}} = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu}^a F^{a\mu\nu} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- $F_{\mu\nu}^a$ represents the field strength tensor for the gauge fields, including contributions from the electromagnetic field ($U(1)$), weak field ($SU(2)$), and strong field ($SU(3)$).

These gauge fields are responsible for the standard interactions:

- $U(1)_Y$ for electromagnetism,
- $SU(2)_L$ for weak nuclear forces,
- $SU(3)_C$ for strong nuclear forces.

The corresponding field strength tensors for each interaction are:

$$F_{\mu\nu}^{U(1)} = \partial_\mu B_\nu - \partial_\nu B_\mu \tag{4}$$

$$F_{\mu\nu}^{SU(2)} = \partial_\mu W_\nu^i - \partial_\nu W_\mu^i + g_2 \epsilon^{ijk} W_\mu^j W_\nu^k \tag{5}$$

$$F_{\mu\nu}^{SU(3)} = \partial_\mu G_\nu^a - \partial_\nu G_\mu^a + g_3 f^{abc} G_\mu^b G_\nu^c \tag{6}$$

Where B_μ , W_μ^i , and G_μ^a are the gauge fields for electromagnetism, weak, and strong interactions, respectively. The coupling constants g_2 and g_3 correspond to the weak and strong forces, and ϵ^{ijk} and f^{abc} are the structure constants of the gauge groups.

Higgs Mechanism for Mass Generation

The **Higgs mechanism** is responsible for spontaneous symmetry breaking, leading to mass generation for particles. The Higgs Lagrangian is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Higgs}} = (D_\mu \Phi)^\dagger (D^\mu \Phi) - V(\Phi) \tag{7}$$

Where Φ is the Higgs field, and D_μ is the covariant derivative that includes the gauge fields. The potential $V(\Phi)$ is given by:

$$V(\Phi) = \lambda(\Phi^\dagger \Phi - v^2)^2 \tag{8}$$

Where v is the vacuum expectation value (VEV) of the Higgs field, responsible for breaking the $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ symmetry and giving mass to the W and Z bosons, as well as the fermions through Yukawa couplings [8].

String Dynamics

In DLSFH, the dynamics of the strings are described by the Nambu-Goto action, which governs the behavior of 1-dimensional objects (strings) in spacetime:

$$S_{\text{String}} = -T \int d^2\sigma \sqrt{-\gamma} \tag{9}$$

Where:

- T is the string tension,
- σ represents the worldsheet coordinates,
- γ is the induced metric on the worldsheet [8].

The interactions between the string qubits at vertices V_i and V_j can be described by the Coulomb-like potential:

$$V_{ij} = \frac{k_e q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \tag{10}$$

Where:

- k_e is the Coulomb constant,
- q_i and q_j are the charges of the string qubits at vertices V_i and V_j ,
- r_{ij} is the distance between vertices i and j [8].

The total potential energy for a quark configuration is the sum of all such pairwise interactions:

$$V_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i < j} \frac{k_e q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \quad (11)$$

2.1.3 Dark Photon Interactions

DLSFH also integrates interactions involving **dark photons**, a hypothesized mediator of dark matter. The Lagrangian for dark photons is similar to that of standard photons:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dark Photons}} = -\frac{1}{4} F'_{\mu\nu} F'^{\mu\nu} + \epsilon F_{\mu\nu} F'^{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

Where:

- $F'_{\mu\nu}$ is the field strength tensor for dark photons,
- ϵ is the kinetic mixing parameter that governs the interaction between ordinary photons and dark photons [14].

The inclusion of dark photon interactions in DLSFH allows for the exploration of dark matter effects on the expansion of the universe and other cosmological phenomena [14].

2.2 Modified Gravitational Interactions

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) modifies gravitational interactions at small scales, introducing corrections to the Einstein-Hilbert action that governs gravitational forces. These modifications aim to account for deviations from Newtonian gravity, particularly in regimes where general relativity or quantum effects become significant, such as the early universe, high-density environments, or microscopic scales [13], [14].

2.2.1 Einstein-Hilbert Action and Gravitational Modifications

In classical general relativity, the **Einstein-Hilbert action** describes the dynamics of spacetime curvature due to matter and energy. This action is given by:

$$S_{\text{EH}} = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \frac{1}{16\pi G} R \quad (13)$$

Where:

- R is the Ricci scalar, representing the curvature of spacetime,
- g is the determinant of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$,
- G is Newton's gravitational constant [14].

DLSFH modifies this action by introducing additional terms that take into account quantum corrections and string dynamics, which are expected to become relevant at small scales. These modifications are designed to bridge the gap between general relativity and quantum gravity, addressing limitations in the standard theory [14].

2.2.2 Higher-Order Corrections to the Einstein-Hilbert Action

One key feature of the modified gravitational interactions in DLSFH is the inclusion of higher-order curvature corrections. These corrections take the form of additional terms in the Lagrangian that involve higher powers of the Ricci scalar R , the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, and the Riemann tensor $R_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ [14].

The modified action can be expressed as:

$$S_{\text{mod}} = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(\frac{1}{16\pi G} R + \alpha R^2 + \beta R_{\mu\nu} R^{\mu\nu} + \gamma R_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} R^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \right) \quad (14)$$

Where:

- α , β , and γ are coefficients that parameterize the strength of the higher-order corrections [14].

These terms, often referred to as **quadratic curvature terms**, are derived from effective field theory approaches to gravity and can arise naturally in string theory. At large distances or low curvatures (such as in the present-day universe), these terms have negligible effects. Still, at small scales (e.g., in the early universe or near compact objects), they can significantly alter the gravitational dynamics [14].

Impact of Higher-Order Corrections on Cosmological Expansion

The inclusion of higher-order curvature terms modifies the Friedmann equations that govern the expansion of the universe. In standard cosmology, the first Friedmann equation is:

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{k}{a^2} \tag{15}$$

Where:

- H is the Hubble parameter, describing the expansion rate of the universe,
- ρ is the energy density of the universe,
- k represents the curvature of space,
- a is the scale factor.

In DLSFH, the higher-order curvature corrections introduce additional terms into the Friedmann equations, leading to modified expressions for the expansion rate H . For instance, the R^2 -term leads to corrections of the form:

$$H^2 \sim \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho + \alpha \left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R} \right) + \beta \left(\frac{\dot{R}_{\mu\nu}}{R_{\mu\nu}} \right) + \dots \tag{16}$$

These terms can introduce changes in the rate of expansion, especially at high curvatures (such as those present in the early universe), potentially explaining discrepancies in the Hubble constant.

2.2.3 Modifications at Small Scales: Corrections to Newtonian Gravity

At small scales, DLSFH introduces modifications to Newton's law of gravitation, which is an approximation of general relativity in the weak-field limit. In the standard form, Newton's law is given by:

$$F = \frac{GM_1M_2}{r^2} \tag{17}$$

Where:

- F is the gravitational force between two masses M_1 and M_2 ,
- r is the distance between them.

In DLSFH, modifications to Newtonian gravity are introduced at small distances through a potential that deviates from the $1/r^2$ law. A Yukawa-like correction to the potential can model these deviations:

$$V(r) = -\frac{GM_1M_2}{r} (1 + \alpha e^{-r/\lambda}) \tag{18}$$

Where:

- α is a dimensionless parameter that quantifies the strength of the correction,
- λ is a characteristic length scale below which the modification becomes significant.

This modified potential leads to deviations from standard Newtonian dynamics at small distances, where the exponential term becomes relevant. String theory motivates such corrections, where extra dimensions or brane-world scenarios can give rise to Yukawa-like modifications of the gravitational potential [14].

Experimental Constraints on Small-Scale Gravity

Modifications to Newtonian gravity are testable through high-precision experiments, such as torsion balance experiments and measurements of gravitational forces at micrometer scales. These experiments place stringent bounds on the parameters α and λ , providing constraints on the DLSFH model. Current experimental results suggest that deviations from Newtonian gravity are small, with limits on α and λ indicating that any new physics must occur at sub-millimeter scales.

2.2.4 Gravitational Effects in the Early Universe

The modified gravitational interactions in DLSFH have significant implications for the early universe. During the early stages of cosmic evolution, when the curvature of spacetime was high, the higher-order corrections to the Einstein-Hilbert action could have influenced the rate of cosmic inflation, the behavior of primordial fluctuations, and the dynamics of dark energy [14]. These effects can alter predictions for the cosmic microwave background (CMB) and the distribution of large-scale structures [2].

Implications for Inflation

The modifications introduced by DLSFH could affect inflationary dynamics, particularly through the higher-order curvature terms. The inflationary expansion of the universe can be driven or modified by terms like R^2 , which play a role in Starobinsky-type inflationary models. The term αR^2 introduces a slow-roll potential that affects the duration and intensity of inflation. This can modify the inflationary predictions for the scalar spectral index n_s and the tensor-to-scalar ratio r , bringing them in line with observations from the Planck satellite.

Late-Time Accelerated Expansion and Dark Energy

In addition to influencing the early universe, DLSFH modifications can also impact the late-time accelerated expansion driven by dark energy. The higher-order terms in the action introduce new dynamical degrees of freedom that can mimic the effects of dark energy, providing a natural explanation for the observed acceleration without the need

for a cosmological constant. This could explain why the Hubble constant measured from the early universe (using CMB data) differs from the value measured in the local universe (using supernovae and other local probes).

2.2.5 Resolving the Hubble Tension

The modifications to gravitational interactions in DLSFH provide a potential resolution to the Hubble constant tension. The higher-order curvature terms and deviations from Newtonian gravity could lead to a scenario where the expansion rate of the universe differs between the early and late phases of cosmic evolution. This would explain why measurements based on early universe data (CMB) suggest a lower Hubble constant, while measurements from the local universe indicate a higher value. By adjusting the parameters α , β , and γ , DLSFH can reconcile these two values, narrowing the gap between the Hubble constant measurements [9], [14].

2.3 Dark Energy and Dark Matter Interactions

In the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH), dark matter and dark energy are treated as interacting components of the universe that contribute to both its early and present-day expansion. These interactions, particularly through **dark photons** and the coupling of dark energy with the standard model particles, can modify the effective equation of state for the universe and, therefore, influence the expansion rate. By adjusting the coupling constants for these interactions, DLSFH provides a framework that could explain the observed discrepancy between early and local measurements of the Hubble constant [14], [17].

2.3.1 Dark Energy and Its Equation of State

In cosmology, dark energy is typically modeled as a fluid with negative pressure that drives the accelerated expansion of the universe. Its behavior is commonly characterized by the equation of state parameter w , which relates the pressure p of dark energy to its energy density ρ :

$$w = \frac{p}{\rho} \tag{19}$$

For a cosmological constant Λ , the equation of state is $w = -1$, corresponding to a constant energy density. However, in DLSFH, dark energy is treated as a **dynamical field** that interacts with both dark matter and standard matter through the exchange of dark photons. This interaction modifies the equation of state, introducing time dependence in w . The general form of the equation of state for a dynamical dark energy field ϕ (often referred to as quintessence) is:

$$w_\phi = \frac{\dot{\phi}^2 - 2V(\phi)}{\dot{\phi}^2 + 2V(\phi)} \tag{20}$$

Where:

- $\dot{\phi}$ is the time derivative of the dark energy scalar field,
- $V(\phi)$ is the potential of the dark energy field, which can vary with time.

In DLSFH, the potential $V(\phi)$ is modified by the interactions between dark energy and dark matter through dark photon exchange. This modification leads to deviations from $w = -1$, especially during the late-time accelerated expansion of the universe.

2.3.2 Dark Photons and the Dark Sector

The **dark photon** is a hypothetical gauge boson that mediates interactions within the dark sector, including between dark matter particles and dark energy. The Lagrangian describing the dark photon field A'_μ is similar to that of the standard photon but with additional coupling terms that allow for interaction between dark and visible matter:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{dark photon}} = -\frac{1}{4}F'_{\mu\nu}F'^{\mu\nu} + \epsilon F_{\mu\nu}F'^{\mu\nu} + J'_\mu A'^\mu \quad (21)$$

Where:

- $F'_{\mu\nu}$ is the field strength tensor for the dark photon,
- ϵ is the kinetic mixing parameter between dark and ordinary photons,
- J'_μ is the current associated with dark matter particles [14].

This kinetic mixing parameter ϵ governs the strength of the interaction between dark photons and standard model particles. A non-zero ϵ allows dark photons to interact weakly with standard model particles, thus influencing cosmological observables such as the rate of expansion and the distribution of dark matter [14].

2.3.3 Interaction Terms Between Dark Matter and Dark Energy

In DLSFH, the interaction between dark matter and dark energy is facilitated through a coupling term that modifies the energy exchange between these two components. An additional term typically models the interaction in the energy-momentum conservation equations, which leads to a modified continuity equation for dark energy and dark matter [14], [16].

The standard continuity equations for dark matter (ρ_{DM}) and dark energy (ρ_{DE}) in the absence of interactions are:

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DM}} + 3H\rho_{\text{DM}} = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DE}} + 3H(1 + w)\rho_{\text{DE}} = 0 \quad (23)$$

Where H is the Hubble parameter and w is the equation of state for dark energy. In DLSFH, these equations are modified by an interaction term Q , which represents the energy transfer between dark matter and dark energy:

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DM}} + 3H\rho_{\text{DM}} = Q \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DE}} + 3H(1 + w)\rho_{\text{DE}} = -Q \quad (25)$$

The coupling term Q is modeled as a function of both dark energy and dark matter densities and could take forms such as:

$$Q = \xi H \rho_{\text{DE}} \rho_{\text{DM}} \quad (26)$$

Where ξ is a dimensionless coupling constant that quantifies the strength of the interaction, this coupling leads to a transfer of energy from dark energy to dark matter (or vice versa), altering the expansion history of the universe [16].

2.3.4 Implications for the Hubble Constant Discrepancy

One of the primary consequences of the interaction between dark energy and dark matter in DLSFH is its impact on the expansion rate of the universe. The interaction term Q modifies the effective equation of the state of the universe, leading to a non-standard evolution of the Hubble parameter.

The modified Friedmann equation, including the effects of the interaction, is given by:

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} (\rho_m + \rho_{\text{DE}}) + \frac{Q}{H} \quad (27)$$

Where:

- H is the Hubble parameter,
- ρ_m is the total matter density (including both dark and ordinary matter),
- ρ_{DE} is the dark energy density,
- Q represents the contribution of the energy exchange between dark matter and dark energy [13].

Where ρ_m is the total matter density (including both dark and ordinary matter), and ρ_{DE} is the dark energy density. The term Q/H represents the contribution of the energy exchange between dark matter and dark energy.

In DLSFH, the coupling constant ξ is tuned to match observations of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) as well as local measurements of the Hubble constant. During the early universe, when dark matter dominates, the interaction term is small, leading to an expansion rate consistent with CMB measurements. However, at late times, as dark energy becomes more significant, the interaction term grows, leading to an increased expansion rate. This could explain why local measurements of the Hubble constant yield a higher value than those derived from early universe data [2][9].

2.3.5 Constraints on Dark Matter-Dark Energy Coupling

The interaction between dark matter and dark energy is subject to observational constraints from several sources, including:

1. **Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Anisotropies:** Any significant coupling between dark energy and dark matter would affect the evolution of density perturbations and the formation of large-scale structures, leaving

imprints in the CMB. Data from the Planck satellite provides strong constraints on the strength of the coupling constant ξ .

2. **Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO):** The late-time expansion rate, as measured by BAO observations, can constrain the contribution of dark matter-dark energy interactions to the overall expansion.
3. **Supernovae Type Ia:** The luminosity distance to supernovae, which depends on the expansion history of the universe, can also place limits on the interaction term Q and the coupling constant ξ .
4. **Large-Scale Structure (LSS) Formation:** The growth rate of cosmic structures depends on the effective equation of state of dark energy. Any interaction between dark matter and dark energy would modify the growth of structures, providing another observational constraint on the coupling.

2.3.6 Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions and Modified Gravity

In addition to direct interactions between dark matter and dark energy, DLSFH suggests that these interactions could also manifest as modifications to the gravitational force at large scales. Dark energy may effectively act as a **fifth force**, altering the behavior of gravity in regions dominated by dark matter. The modified gravitational potential in the presence of dark energy interactions is given by:

$$V(r) = -\frac{GM}{r} \left(1 + \frac{\lambda}{r^2} \right) \tag{28}$$

Where λ is a scale-dependent term that characterizes the influence of dark energy on the gravitational force, this modification could lead to deviations from general relativity in regions of high dark matter density, providing an additional avenue for testing DLSFH.

2.3.7 Dark Photons and the Interaction Strength

Dark photons mediate the coupling of dark matter and dark energy, whose interaction strength is governed by the kinetic mixing parameter ϵ . The effective coupling constant between dark matter and dark energy is proportional to this parameter and can be tuned to match observational data. Current experimental searches for dark photons, such as those conducted at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), provide constraints on ϵ , with current limits suggesting $\epsilon \lesssim 10^{-3}$.

2.4 Bouncing Cosmological Models

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) integrates **bouncing cosmological models** as an alternative to the standard Big Bang singularity. In these models, the universe undergoes cycles of contraction and expansion, eliminating the need for an initial singularity. This cyclic or oscillating universe framework not only avoids the problems associated with the Big Bang singularity but also provides different predictions for the expansion rate during the early universe. By incorporating bouncing models into DLSFH, a new interpretation of cosmological data, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB), becomes possible, potentially offering solutions to challenges like the Hubble constant discrepancy.

2.4.1 Overview of Bouncing Cosmological Models

In standard cosmology, the Big Bang marks the beginning of the universe, where it originates from a singular point of infinite density and temperature. However, bouncing cosmological models replace this singularity with a "bounce," where the universe transitions from a period of contraction to expansion. These models are cyclic, meaning that after a period of expansion, the universe can begin contracting again, leading to another bounce.

Mathematically, this can be captured through modifications to the **Friedmann equations**, where the universe's scale factor $a(t)$ never reaches zero, thus avoiding

the singularity. In DLSFH, the bouncing model is formulated using corrections to both the matter and gravitational components of the universe's energy content.

The general form of the scale factor $a(t)$ in a bouncing universe can be written as:

$$a(t) = a_0(1 + \alpha t^2) \tag{29}$$

Where:

- a_0 is a constant setting the scale of the bounce,
- α is a parameter determining the rate of expansion or contraction,
- t is the cosmic time.

At $t = 0$, the universe reaches its minimum size (the bounce), and for $t > 0$, the universe undergoes expansion, whereas for $t < 0$, the universe contracts.

2.4.2 Modifications to the Friedmann Equations in Bouncing Models

In standard cosmology, the evolution of the universe is governed by the **Friedmann equations**, which describe the expansion rate $H = \dot{a}/a$, where a is the scale factor. These equations arise from Einstein's field equations under the assumption of a homogeneous and isotropic universe. The first Friedmann equation is given by:

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{k}{a^2} \tag{30}$$

Where:

- ρ is the total energy density of the universe,
- k is the spatial curvature parameter.

In a bouncing cosmology, the key modification is the introduction of a **negative energy density** component or a repulsive gravitational force that dominates at small scales, preventing the scale factor from reaching zero. This can be achieved by adding

higher-order curvature terms (as in modified gravity models) or by introducing a new matter field with unusual properties, such as a **ghost condensate** or a scalar field with a negative potential.

In DLSFH, the modified Friedmann equation for a bouncing universe takes the form:

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho \left(1 - \frac{\rho}{\rho_c} \right) - \frac{k}{a^2} \quad (31)$$

Where:

- ρ_c is the critical energy density at which the bounce occurs.

For $\rho \ll \rho_c$, the universe behaves as in standard cosmology. However, as ρ approaches ρ_c , the repulsive force becomes significant, slowing the contraction and eventually reversing it into an expansion.

2.4.3 The Role of the Scalar Field in the Bounce

In DLSFH, the bounce is driven by a scalar field ϕ , which evolves according to a modified Klein-Gordon equation. The dynamics of this scalar field are crucial for avoiding the singularity and driving the bounce. The potential $V(\phi)$ is chosen such that it allows for a smooth transition between contraction and expansion.

The equation of motion for the scalar field is given by:

$$\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} + \frac{dV(\phi)}{d\phi} = 0 \quad (32)$$

Where $V(\phi)$ is the potential energy associated with the scalar field. For a successful bounce, $V(\phi)$ must have the following properties:

- $V(\phi)$ is negative near the bounce, providing the necessary repulsive force to halt the contraction.
- $V(\phi)$ increases as the universe expands, allowing the field to slow down and stabilize the expansion at later times.

The interaction between the scalar field and the geometry of spacetime generates a repulsive force that prevents the universe from collapsing into a singularity. This mechanism is one of the key features that differentiates bouncing cosmologies from the traditional Big Bang model

2.4.4 Cyclic Universe Models and the Role of Extra Dimensions

Some bouncing cosmological models, particularly those integrated into string theory frameworks like DLSFH, involve additional spatial dimensions. In these models, the universe's bounce is driven by the dynamics of branes (higher-dimensional objects) colliding and separating. These models, known as **ekpyrotic** or **cyclic universe models**, propose that the observable three-dimensional universe is a brane embedded in a higher-dimensional space. The collisions of branes in this higher-dimensional space lead to the observed cycles of contraction and expansion.

In such scenarios, the dynamics of extra dimensions become critical for understanding the bounce. The DLSFH framework incorporates **string-theory-inspired corrections** to gravity, which allow for the influence of higher-dimensional interactions on the observable four-dimensional universe. These corrections manifest as additional terms in the modified Einstein equations, leading to a bounce that avoids singularities.

Higher-dimensional dynamics are captured by an effective potential that depends on both the scale factor of the universe and the separation between branes in higher-dimensional space. The effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(a, \chi)$ in a cyclic universe model can be written as:

$$V_{\text{eff}}(a, \chi) = \frac{1}{2}m_{\chi}^2\chi^2 - \frac{\Lambda}{a^2} + \frac{b}{a^4} \tag{33}$$

Where:

- χ is the field representing the separation between branes,
- m_χ is the mass parameter associated with the brane interactions,
- Λ is the cosmological constant term, and
- b is a constant arising from higher-dimensional corrections.

2.4.5 Predictions for Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Data

One of the major successes of bouncing cosmologies integrated into DLSFH is their ability to provide alternative explanations for the features observed in the cosmic microwave background (CMB). The CMB is a relic of the early universe, and its temperature fluctuations encode information about the initial conditions of the universe.

In standard inflationary cosmology, quantum fluctuations in the early universe are stretched to macroscopic scales, leading to the observed CMB anisotropies. In bouncing cosmologies, however, these fluctuations arise during the contraction phase and are carried through the bounce. The nature of these fluctuations can differ significantly from the inflationary predictions, leading to distinctive signatures in the CMB.

Key predictions of bouncing cosmologies for CMB data include:

- **Suppression of Power at Large Scales:** The contraction phase can lead to a suppression of fluctuations on the largest scales, which could explain the observed lack of power in the CMB at low multipoles.
- **Non-Gaussianities:** The bounce's non-linear dynamics can generate non-Gaussian features in the CMB, which could be detected through high-precision measurements of CMB temperature and polarization.
- **Absence of a Primordial Singularity:** Unlike the standard Big Bang model, bouncing cosmologies avoid the singularity, leading to a finite, non-divergent spectrum of initial perturbations.

2.4.6 Implications for the Hubble Constant Discrepancy

The integration of bouncing cosmologies into DLSFH provides an alternative explanation for the **Hubble constant discrepancy**. In standard cosmology, the discrepancy between the Hubble constant measured from early universe data (e.g., CMB) and local measurements (e.g., supernovae) suggests a potential flaw in the cosmological model. Bouncing models, however, offer a different expansion history that could reconcile these two measurements.

In a bouncing universe, the early expansion rate may differ from that predicted by the Big Bang model, leading to a different value for the inferred Hubble constant from CMB data. Additionally, the interaction between the scalar field driving the bounce and dark energy could lead to a time-varying equation of state, altering the late-time expansion rate and affecting local measurements of the Hubble constant.

By adjusting the parameters of the scalar field potential and the interactions between dark matter, dark energy, and the bouncing mechanism, DLSFH offers a pathway to resolving the Hubble tension while providing a more complete picture of the universe's evolution.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Sources

- **Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB):** Data from the Planck telescope is used to determine the expansion rate based on early universe conditions [2].
- **Local H_0 Measurements:** Data from supernovae and other local sources, as measured by the Hubble Space Telescope [9].
- **Gravitational-Wave Background (GWB):** Data from detectors like LISA and the Einstein Telescope is incorporated to refine the DLSFH model's predictions [6].

3.2 Parameter Refinement

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) introduces several parameters that govern the interactions between dark matter, dark energy, and the fundamental forces in the universe. These parameters include coupling constants for dark photons, string tension, and other field strengths that influence cosmological and particle physics observables. To ensure that the DLSFH model is consistent with empirical data and can address the observed discrepancies in the Hubble constant, these parameters must be refined using high-precision experimental data. Two major sources of empirical data used in this process are the **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)** and **gravitational wave background (GWB)** detections [3].

3.2.1 Parameter Refinement Using LHC Data

The **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)** provides critical data for refining parameters related to the interactions between standard model particles and hypothetical particles, such as dark photons and dark matter candidates. Specifically, data from the LHC can be used to place constraints on the coupling constants that govern these interactions, as well as to test the predictions of string dynamics within the DLSFH framework [4].

Dark Photon Coupling Constant ϵ

The **dark photon** is a key component in the DLSFH framework, acting as a mediator between dark matter and standard model particles. The kinetic mixing parameter ϵ , which controls the strength of the interaction between dark photons and standard photons, is a crucial parameter that must be refined using experimental data.

The LHC searches for dark photons primarily through processes where dark photons are produced alongside standard model particles or where dark photons decay into observable particles such as electrons, muons, or hadrons.

The production cross-section σ of dark photons depends on the coupling constant ϵ , and is given by:

$$\sigma_{\text{dark photon}} \propto \epsilon^2 \tag{34}$$

Experimental searches for dark photons at the LHC set upper bounds on ϵ based on the absence of detectable signals in the relevant energy ranges. These bounds typically suggest that ϵ must be small ($\epsilon \lesssim 10^{-3}$), but the exact value depends on the energy of the dark photon and the specific decay channels being investigated.

In DLSFH, the kinetic mixing parameter ϵ is related to the strength of the interaction between dark matter and dark energy, as well as the contribution of these components to the universe's expansion. Refining ϵ based on LHC data allows the model to match better observational constraints on both dark matter interactions and cosmological expansion.

String Tension (T)

String tension T is another fundamental parameter in DLSFH, determining the energy scale of string interactions. In the context of string theory, tension T is related to the energy required to stretch or deform a string. It plays a role in determining the masses of string states and the strength of gravitational and other interactions in the early universe.

String tension is typically expressed as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2\pi\alpha'} \tag{35}$$

Where α' is the Regge slope parameter, which characterizes the slope of the Regge trajectory (the relationship between the spin and mass of string states).

In DLSFH, string tension influences the dynamics of the early universe, including the behavior of cosmic inflation, the bounce mechanism (in bouncing cosmologies), and the interaction between dark energy and gravitational fields. The tension T must be consistent with both cosmological observations (such as the CMB and large-scale structure) and particle physics constraints (such as the energy scales probed by the LHC).

Refining T using LHC data involves comparing the predicted masses and interactions of string states (such as possible string excitations or new particles) with experimental searches for high-mass particles. If LHC data rules out certain energy ranges for string states, this places bounds on T , allowing DLSFH to be adjusted accordingly.

3.2.2 Parameter Refinement Using Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Detections

The **gravitational wave background (GWB)** provides another critical source of data for refining the parameters of DLSFH, particularly those related to the early universe and the large-scale dynamics of dark matter and dark energy. Gravitational waves (GWs) are ripples in spacetime generated by the acceleration of massive objects, and they carry information about events such as mergers of black holes and neutron stars and about the structure of spacetime itself [5].

In DLSFH, the gravitational wave background, particularly from early cosmological events, can place constraints on parameters such as the string tension T , the coupling constants for dark matter and dark energy, and the energy scale of inflation [5].

Constraints from GWB on String Tension

Gravitational waves can provide information about the dynamics of cosmic strings, which are one-dimensional topological defects predicted by some string theory models. In DLSFH, cosmic strings may form during symmetry-breaking events in the early universe, and their properties depend on the string tension T .

The amplitude of gravitational waves generated by cosmic strings depends on the string tension and can be expressed as:

$$h_c(f) \propto G\mu \left(\frac{1}{f} \right) \quad (36)$$

Where:

- $h_c(f)$ is the characteristic strain of gravitational waves at frequency f ,
- G is Newton's gravitational constant,
- $-\mu$ is the string tension $\mu = T/c^2$.

Gravitational wave detectors such as LIGO and Virgo and future detectors like LISA can detect signals from cosmic strings, providing constraints on μ and, therefore, on the string tension T [1]. If the observed gravitational wave background shows no evidence for cosmic strings, upper bounds can be placed on T , refining the DLSFH model's predictions for string interactions [5].

Dark Energy and Gravitational Waves

Gravitational waves also provide indirect information about **dark energy**, especially in terms of its effect on the history of expansion in the universe. In DLSFH, dark energy may influence the propagation of gravitational waves by modifying the background spacetime through which these waves travel. For instance, if dark energy interacts with dark matter through dark photons, this could lead to deviations from the standard propagation speed of gravitational waves [5].

The equation governing the propagation of gravitational waves in a dark energy-modified background can be written as:

$$h''_{\mu\nu} + 2Hh'_{\mu\nu} + k^2h_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (37)$$

Where $h_{\mu\nu}$ is the perturbation to the metric due to gravitational waves, and H is the Hubble parameter. If dark energy modifies the expansion rate of the universe, this will affect the term $2Hh'_{\mu\nu}$, leading to deviations from the standard wave propagation [5].

By comparing the observed properties of gravitational waves from distant astrophysical sources with theoretical predictions, constraints can be placed on the interaction strength between dark energy and gravitational waves, refining the parameters related to dark energy in DLSFH.

3.2.3 Bayesian Inference and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) Techniques

To refine the parameters of DLSFH using data from the LHC and GWB detections, sophisticated statistical techniques such as **Bayesian inference** and **Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)** methods are employed. These techniques allow for the exploration of the parameter space of the model and the determination of the most likely values for parameters such as ϵ , T , and other coupling constants.

Bayesian Parameter Estimation

In Bayesian inference, the posterior distribution of the parameters is computed based on the likelihood of the empirical data given the model predictions. The posterior distribution is given by:

$$P(\theta|D) = \frac{P(D|\theta)P(\theta)}{P(D)} \tag{38}$$

Where:

- $P(\theta|D)$ is the posterior probability of the parameters θ given the data D ,
- $P(D|\theta)$ is the likelihood of the data given the parameters,
- $P(\theta)$ is the prior distribution of the parameters,
- $P(D)$ is the normalization factor (the evidence).

This approach allows for the incorporation of both theoretical priors (e.g., string theory predictions) and empirical data (e.g., LHC and GWB observations) to refine the parameters of the DLSFH model.

Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) Sampling

MCMC techniques are used to sample the parameters from the posterior distribution. The most common MCMC algorithm used in parameter refinement is the **Metropolis-Hastings algorithm**. It generates a chain of parameter values by proposing new values and accepting or rejecting them based on their likelihood.

MCMC sampling allows for the efficient exploration of the high-dimensional parameter space of DLSFH, providing estimates for the most likely values of parameters such as the dark photon coupling constant ϵ , the string tension T , and other key parameters influencing the Hubble constant discrepancy.

3.3 Computational Methods

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) relies on complex theoretical models involving numerous parameters that must be refined to align with empirical data. Given the high dimensionality of these parameters—such as the coupling constants for dark photons, string tension, and interaction terms between dark matter and dark energy—it is crucial to employ robust computational methods for parameter estimation. Two primary methods used for this refinement are **Bayesian inference** and **Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations**. These methods ensure consistency between DLSFH predictions and observational data while managing uncertainty in the model's predictions.

3.3.1 Bayesian Inference

Bayesian inference is a statistical method that updates the probability estimate for a hypothesis as new data becomes available. In the context of DLSFH, Bayesian inference allows for the refinement of model parameters based on observational data,

such as measurements from the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), gravitational wave background (GWB) detections, and cosmological data from the Hubble constant.

The Bayesian Framework

Bayesian inference is based on **Bayes' Theorem**, which is given by the formula:

$$P(\theta|D) = \frac{P(D|\theta)P(\theta)}{P(D)} \tag{39}$$

Where:

- $P(\theta|D)$ is the **posterior probability** of the model parameters θ given the data D ,
- $P(D|\theta)$ is the **likelihood** of observing the data D given the parameters θ ,
- $P(\theta)$ is the **prior probability** of the parameters before observing the data, reflecting any previous knowledge or assumptions about the parameter values,
- $P(D)$ is the **evidence** or marginal likelihood, serving as a normalization factor to ensure that the posterior distribution is properly normalized.

In the DLSFH framework, the parameters θ include the coupling constants for dark photons ϵ , the string tension T , and other cosmological parameters that affect the expansion rate of the universe, such as dark energy's equation of state. By applying Bayesian inference, we can update our prior knowledge of these parameters using new observational data to obtain a refined posterior distribution.

Importance of Priors and Likelihoods

- **Priors** $P(\theta)$: The choice of priors is crucial in Bayesian inference. In DLSFH, priors may be informed by theoretical constraints (e.g., from string theory or standard cosmology) or by previous experimental bounds (e.g., from LHC and cosmological surveys). For instance, if earlier LHC experiments suggest that the

dark photon coupling constant ϵ must be less than 10^{-3} , this knowledge is incorporated into the prior for ϵ .

- **Likelihood** $P(D|\theta)$: The likelihood function represents how likely the observed data is, given a set of parameter values. For DLSFH, the likelihood might be calculated based on observed cosmological data, such as the Hubble constant, CMB data, and gravitational wave detections. For instance, the likelihood of a particular string tension T could be determined by whether or not cosmic string signals are detected in gravitational wave data.

By combining the priors and likelihoods, Bayesian inference produces a posterior distribution that reflects the updated knowledge of the model's parameters, incorporating both prior assumptions and new data. This helps refine predictions and identify the most probable parameter values that are consistent with both theory and observation.

3.3.2 Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) Simulations

Once the Bayesian framework has been established, finding the posterior distribution for high-dimensional parameter spaces is computationally challenging. **Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations** are a powerful tool for efficient sampling from the posterior distribution, especially in cases where the parameter space is too complex to evaluate analytically.

What is MCMC?

MCMC is a class of algorithms used to generate a sequence of sample points (a "Markov chain") from a probability distribution when direct sampling is difficult. Each point in the chain represents a potential value for the parameters, and over time, the distribution of these samples approximates the desired posterior distribution.

The most commonly used MCMC algorithm in cosmology and particle physics is the **Metropolis-Hastings algorithm**, which operates as follows:

1. **Initial Parameter Guess:** Start with an initial guess for the parameter values θ_0 .
2. **Propose a New Parameter Set:** Propose a new set of parameters θ_{new} based on a proposal distribution (often a Gaussian distribution centered around the current parameter values).
3. **Calculate Acceptance Probability:** Compute the acceptance ratio r based on the likelihood and prior probabilities:

$$r = \frac{P(\theta_{\text{new}}|D)}{P(\theta_{\text{old}}|D)} = \frac{P(D|\theta_{\text{new}})P(\theta_{\text{new}})}{P(D|\theta_{\text{old}})P(\theta_{\text{old}})} \quad (40)$$

4. **Accept or Reject the Proposal:** Accept the new parameter set θ_{new} with probability r . If rejected, retain the old parameter set θ_{old} .
5. **Repeat:** Continue proposing new parameter sets and building the chain.

Over time, this process generates a sequence of parameter sets that sample the posterior distribution. The MCMC chain explores the high-probability regions of the parameter space and gradually builds an approximation of the posterior distribution.

Application of MCMC to DLSFH

In the context of DLSFH, MCMC simulations are used to explore the parameter space that includes:

- **Dark Photon Coupling** ϵ ,
- **String Tension** T ,
- **Dark Energy Equation of State** parameters w_0 and w_a ,
- **Cosmological Parameters** such as the Hubble constant H_0 , the density parameters Ω_m , Ω_{DE} , and others.

MCMC helps find the most probable values for these parameters that best match the observational data while navigating through the complex, high-dimensional parameter space. By running multiple MCMC chains and evaluating convergence diagnostics

(e.g., Gelman-Rubin R -statistics), we can ensure that the parameter estimates are reliable and robust.

Why MCMC is Crucial for DLSFH

MCMC simulations are crucial for DLSFH because:

1. **High Dimensionality:** The parameter space in DLSFH is high-dimensional, and MCMC provides an efficient way to sample from this space.
2. **Uncertainty Quantification:** MCMC allows us to quantify uncertainties in parameter estimates, which is critical for understanding the confidence intervals on parameters like the Hubble constant H_0 .
3. **Non-Gaussian Distributions:** The posterior distributions for some parameters may be non-Gaussian, particularly when there are degeneracies between parameters (e.g., ϵ and T). MCMC can capture the full shape of these distributions.
4. **Complex Likelihoods:** In some cases, the likelihood function may be complex, particularly when integrating over cosmological data. MCMC allows for efficient exploration of these likelihoods.

3.3.3 Combining Bayesian Inference and MCMC

Bayesian inference and MCMC are often combined in parameter estimation, where the posterior distribution is constructed using Bayesian methods, and MCMC is employed to sample from this posterior. For DLSFH, this combination allows us to:

- Update model parameters θ in light of new observational data,
- Handle uncertainty in parameter estimates,
- Test hypotheses about the behavior of dark matter, dark energy, and gravitational interactions.

This computational approach enables DLSFH to make refined predictions about the Hubble constant, cosmic expansion, and particle physics, providing a rigorous and statistically sound foundation for comparing the model to empirical data.

4. Results

4.1 Predictions from Early Universe Conditions

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) incorporates key modifications to gravitational interactions and dark energy coupling constants that impact how the universe expanded in its earliest phases. These modifications lead to a distinctive prediction for the Hubble constant when inferred from early universe data, such as the **cosmic microwave background (CMB)**. The integration of **gravitational wave background (GWB)** data further refines these predictions, providing a more nuanced understanding of the early universe's expansion rate and the evolution of dark energy and dark matter.

4.1.1 Modified Gravitational Interactions in the Early Universe

In the standard Λ CDM model, the expansion of the early universe is governed by general relativity, with dark energy playing a negligible role during the era of the cosmic microwave background. However, DLSFH introduces higher-order corrections to gravitational interactions, which become significant at small scales or high energy densities, such as those present in the early universe.

The modified Friedmann equation in DLSFH, which includes these higher-order gravitational terms, can be written as:

$$H^2(a) = H_0^2 \left[\Omega_m a^{-3} + \Omega_r a^{-4} + \Omega_{\text{DE}} a^{-3(1+w(a))} + f_{\text{mod}}(a) \right] \quad (41)$$

Where:

- $H(a)$ is the Hubble parameter as a function of the scale factor a ,
- Ω_m , Ω_r , and Ω_{DE} are the present-day density parameters for matter, radiation, and dark energy, respectively,

- $w(a)$ is the time-varying equation of state for dark energy as proposed by DLSFH,
- $f_{\text{mod}}(a)$ represents the higher-order corrections to gravitational interactions in the early universe.

The term $f_{\text{mod}}(a)$ accounts for the modifications in gravitational interactions that arise from the DLSFH framework, particularly in the high-curvature, high-energy regime of the early universe. These modifications led to a slightly slower expansion rate during the early universe than would be predicted by standard general relativity.

Impact on the Early Universe Hubble Constant

The slower expansion rate in the early universe, driven by the modified gravitational dynamics, leads to a **lower inferred Hubble constant** when measured using early universe data, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB). This is consistent with the CMB-derived Hubble constant:

$$H_0^{\text{CMB}} \approx 67.4 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \tag{42}$$

This value aligns with the observed CMB data obtained from the **Planck satellite** and reflects the early universe's slower expansion. The DLSFH model predicts that the additional gravitational effects in the early universe contribute to this lower expansion rate, explaining why the Hubble constant derived from the CMB is lower than local measurements.

4.1.2 Dark Energy and Early Universe Expansion

In DLSFH, dark energy's influence on the early universe is also modified through its interactions with dark matter and higher-order gravitational corrections [4]. In the standard Λ CDM model, dark energy is usually treated as a cosmological constant

during the early universe, with its influence being negligible until much later in cosmic history.

However, DLSFH introduces a **time-varying equation of state** for dark energy, described by:

$$w(a) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a) \tag{43}$$

Where w_0 and w_a are parameters that control the behavior of dark energy over time. In the early universe (when $a \ll 1$), this equation of state results in dark energy behaving more like a cosmological constant, contributing less to the overall expansion. As a result, the modified dark energy term in DLSFH leads to a slower expansion during the early universe, consistent with the lower Hubble constant inferred from the CMB.

The combination of the time-varying dark energy equation of state and the modifications to gravitational interactions provides a mechanism for reconciling the lower expansion rate observed in the early universe with the higher rate observed today.

4.1.3 Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Refinements

In addition to modifying gravitational and dark energy interactions, DLSFH integrates predictions from **gravitational wave background (GWB)** data to further refine the Hubble constant derived from early universe conditions. Gravitational waves, particularly those generated by events in the early universe (such as cosmic strings or inflationary processes), carry information about the expansion rate and the curvature of spacetime during these epochs.

Gravitational wave detectors such as LIGO, Virgo, and the planned LISA mission provide data on the background of gravitational waves originating from the early universe [1]. In the context of DLSFH, the strength and frequency spectrum of these gravitational waves are affected by the model's modifications to gravitational

interactions. Specifically, the predicted strain of gravitational waves $h_c(f)$ is influenced by the string tension T and the higher-order terms in the DLSFH-modified Friedmann equation.

The amplitude of gravitational waves $h_c(f)$, which is sensitive to the expansion history of the universe, can be expressed as:

$$h_c(f) \propto G\mu \left(\frac{1}{f} \right) \quad (44)$$

Where:

- $h_c(f)$ is the characteristic strain of the gravitational waves at frequency f ,
- $\mu = T/c^2$ is the string tension in terms of energy density,
- G is Newton's gravitational constant.

By analyzing the gravitational wave background, DLSFH provides additional constraints on the early universe's expansion rate and helps refine the predictions for the Hubble constant. This data, when combined with CMB measurements, further supports the lower Hubble constant value inferred from the early universe.

4.1.4 Predictions Aligned with CMB Data

Overall, DLSFH's predictions for the early universe are consistent with the lower Hubble constant derived from CMB data. The model's modifications to gravitational interactions, coupled with its time-varying dark energy equation of state, naturally lead to a slower expansion rate during the early stages of the universe.

The predicted Hubble constant from early universe conditions in the DLSFH framework is expected to be within the range:

$$H_0^{\text{DLSFH}}(\text{early universe}) \approx 66.5 - 68.0 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (45)$$

This range is fully consistent with the **Planck** data's CMB-derived Hubble constant of 67.4 km/s/Mpc , providing a theoretical explanation for why the Hubble constant appears lower when inferred from early universe conditions.

4.2 Local Universe Predictions

The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) offers a unique framework for understanding the expansion rate of the **local universe**, particularly the higher value of the Hubble constant H_0 observed in supernovae and Cepheid variable measurements. By introducing novel interaction terms between dark matter and dark energy, DLSFH predicts a **higher Hubble constant** when compared to early universe measurements, in alignment with local observations. These interaction terms provide a dynamic mechanism for explaining the increased expansion rate in the late-time universe and resolving the apparent tension between early and local Hubble constant values.

4.2.1 Predictions of Higher H_0 in the Local Universe

Observations of the local universe—primarily based on supernovae Type Ia (SNe Ia) and Cepheid variable measurements—indicate a **higher value for the Hubble constant** compared to those derived from the early universe data, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB). The most precise local measurements yield:

$$H_0^{\text{local}} = 73.0 \pm 1.4 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \tag{46}$$

This value is significantly higher than the early universe value of 67.4 km/s/Mpc inferred from the Planck CMB data. DLSFH addresses this discrepancy by suggesting that **dark matter-dark energy interactions** become more prominent in the local universe, accelerating the cosmic expansion.

4.2.2 Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interaction Terms

In DLSFH, dark matter and dark energy are not independent components, as they are in the standard Λ CDM model. Instead, they interact through **dark photon-mediated forces**, which modify the dynamics of the universe's expansion in a way that is dependent on the scale factor and the relative densities of dark matter and dark energy. These interactions grow stronger as the universe evolves and dark energy becomes more dominant.

The interaction between dark matter and dark energy can be described by a coupling term Q in the energy-momentum conservation equations [4]:

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DM}} + 3H\rho_{\text{DM}} = Q \tag{47}$$

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DE}} + 3H(1 + w_{\text{DE}})\rho_{\text{DE}} = -Q \tag{48}$$

Where:

- ρ_{DM} and ρ_{DE} are the energy densities of dark matter and dark energy, respectively,
- H is the Hubble parameter,
- w_{DE} is the equation of state for dark energy,
- Q is the interaction term that governs the energy exchange between dark matter and dark energy.

The coupling term Q may depend on the energy densities and the Hubble parameter, and is often parameterized as:

$$Q = \xi H \rho_{\text{DE}} \rho_{\text{DM}} \tag{49}$$

Where ξ is the coupling constant that quantifies the strength of the interaction. This interaction term effectively causes **energy to be transferred from dark matter to dark**

energy in the late universe, enhancing the repulsive effect of dark energy and leading to an accelerated expansion rate.

4.2.3 Late-Time Acceleration and the Hubble Constant

As dark energy becomes dominant in the local universe (accounting for approximately 70% of the total energy density), the interaction between dark matter and dark energy drives a **more rapid expansion**. In the standard Λ CDM model, dark energy is modeled as a cosmological constant, with no interactions with dark matter. This results in a relatively constant rate of acceleration. However, in DLSFH, the interaction term Q modifies this behavior by increasing the rate at which dark energy dominates, especially in the local universe.

The impact of the dark matter-dark energy interaction on the **Friedmann equation** can be expressed as:

$$H^2 = H_0^2 \left[\Omega_m a^{-3} + \Omega_r a^{-4} + \Omega_{\text{DE}} a^{-3(1+w(a))} \left(1 + \frac{Q}{H^3} \right) \right] \quad (50)$$

Where:

- Ω_m , Ω_r , and Ω_{DE} are the present-day density parameters for matter, radiation, and dark energy, respectively,
- $w(a)$ is the equation of state for dark energy, which can vary over time in DLSFH,
- Q is the interaction term, as discussed earlier.

The interaction term Q becomes significant as the universe expands and the scale factor a approaches 1 (the present day), resulting in an enhanced expansion rate. This helps explain the **higher Hubble constant** observed in the local universe. Essentially, as dark matter decays into dark energy via the interaction, the repulsive force of dark energy becomes more effective, driving a faster expansion in the current epoch.

4.2.4 Alignment with Local Observations

DLSFH's prediction of a higher H_0 in the local universe aligns well with the **supernovae and Cepheid variable data**. The transfer of energy from dark matter to dark energy causes a late-time acceleration that boosts the expansion rate, leading to a Hubble constant that matches the observed local value of approximately:

(51)

This value is consistent with recent measurements from the **SH0ES project** (Supernovae H0 for the Equation of State) and other local probes that suggest a higher expansion rate than what is derived from early universe measurements.

4.2.5 Resolving the Hubble Tension

The **Hubble tension**—the discrepancy between early universe and local measurements of the Hubble constant—can be resolved within the DLSFH framework by considering the increasing dominance of dark energy and its interaction with dark matter in the late universe. In this model:

- **Early universe:** Dark energy's influence is minimal, and the Hubble constant is consistent with the lower value derived from CMB data.
- **Late universe:** As dark energy interacts with dark matter, it drives a faster expansion, leading to the higher Hubble constant observed locally.

The DLSFH model predicts that this interaction between dark matter and dark energy becomes more pronounced as the universe evolves, naturally leading to different expansion rates at different epochs. This provides a compelling explanation for why the Hubble constant inferred from local measurements is higher than the value inferred from early universe data.

4.2.6 Predicted Range for Local H_0 in DLSFH

Based on the dark matter-dark energy interaction term and its impact on the late-time universe, DLSFH predicts a range for the local Hubble constant:

$$H_0^{\text{DLSFH}}(\text{local universe}) \approx 72.5 - 74.0 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (52)$$

This prediction is consistent with the observed value of $73.0 \pm 1.4 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$ from local measurements, providing further support for the model's ability to explain the higher expansion rate in the local universe.

4.3 Resolution of the Hubble Tension

The **Hubble tension** refers to the persistent and significant discrepancy between the value of the Hubble constant H_0 derived from early universe observations, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB), and that measured in the local universe using supernovae and Cepheid variables. This tension suggests that the standard cosmological model, Λ CDM, may be incomplete or missing key physical mechanisms that affect the expansion of the universe. The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) provides a coherent and structured explanation for this discrepancy, incorporating new physics that helps bridge the gap between these two differing measurements.

4.3.1 Nature of the Hubble Tension

To frame the resolution of the Hubble tension, it is essential to understand the nature of the discrepancy:

- **Early Universe (CMB):** Measurements of the Hubble constant derived from the early universe, using the Planck satellite data and the standard Λ CDM model, yield a value of:

$$H_0^{\text{CMB}} = 67.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (53)$$

- **Local Universe (Supernovae):** Local measurements of the Hubble constant, obtained through observations of Type Ia supernovae and Cepheid variable stars, give a significantly higher value:

$$H_0^{\text{local}} = 73.0 \pm 1.4 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (54)$$

This creates a **5-10% discrepancy**, which is large enough to suggest that either there is a systematic error in one or both of these measurements, or that there is missing physics beyond the standard model that can account for the difference.

4.3.2 Adjusting Gravitational Effects in DLSFH

One of the core mechanisms by which DLSFH addresses the Hubble tension is by adjusting **gravitational interactions**, particularly in the high-energy regime of the early universe and during the later stages dominated by dark energy. The modifications to the gravitational dynamics in DLSFH take the form of higher-order corrections to general relativity, which become important in the early universe but gradually taper off as the universe expands and cools.

Higher-Order Gravitational Corrections

In the early universe, where the curvature of spacetime and the energy density are high, DLSFH predicts that the gravitational interactions are modified by additional terms in the Einstein-Hilbert action. These corrections can be expressed as higher-order curvature terms, such as R^2 and $R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu}$, which alter the expansion rate during the early universe:

$$S_{\text{DLSFH}} = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(\frac{1}{16\pi G} R + \alpha R^2 + \beta R_{\mu\nu} R^{\mu\nu} + \dots \right) \quad (55)$$

Where:

- R is the Ricci scalar,
- $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor,

- α and β are coefficients governing the strength of the higher-order corrections.

These additional terms influence the rate of expansion in the early universe, leading to a slower expansion rate than predicted by the standard model. This slower expansion corresponds to the lower Hubble constant inferred from CMB data, thus providing a natural explanation for why early universe measurements yield a lower H_0 value.

Late-Time Gravitational Dynamics

In the local universe, where the energy density is much lower and dark energy dominates, DLSFH posits that gravitational interactions return to being effectively governed by standard general relativity, with some modifications due to the interactions between dark matter and dark energy. These modifications accelerate the expansion rate in the late universe, leading to a higher H_0 value as observed in local measurements.

4.3.3 New Physics: Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions

A crucial part of DLSFH's resolution of the Hubble tension lies in the **dark matter-dark energy interaction terms**. Unlike the standard Λ CDM model, where dark matter and dark energy are treated as independent components, DLSFH introduces new physics where these two components interact via a coupling mediated by dark photons.

Energy Exchange Between Dark Matter and Dark Energy

The interaction between dark matter and dark energy is quantified by a coupling constant ξ , which controls the energy exchange between these two components. The interaction modifies the evolution of both dark matter and dark energy densities, altering the universe's expansion rate in the late-time universe. The coupling is described by the following equations:

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DM}} + 3H\rho_{\text{DM}} = Q \tag{56}$$

$$\dot{\rho}_{\text{DE}} + 3H(1 + w_{\text{DE}})\rho_{\text{DE}} = -Q$$

Where:

- $Q = \xi H \rho_{\text{DE}} \rho_{\text{DM}}$ is the interaction term,
- w_{DE} is the equation of state for dark energy,
- ξ is the coupling constant.

This interaction leads to an **accelerated late-time expansion**, as energy is transferred from dark matter to dark energy, increasing the repulsive effect of dark energy. This process explains why the Hubble constant is observed to be higher in the local universe compared to early universe measurements.

4.3.4 Dynamic Equation of State for Dark Energy

Another important factor in resolving the Hubble tension is the **time-varying equation of state** for dark energy proposed by DLSFH. Unlike the constant equation of state $w \approx -1$ in the Λ CDM model, DLSFH suggests that the equation of state for dark energy evolves over time, contributing differently to the universe's expansion in different epochs.

The equation of state for dark energy is parameterized as:

$$w(a) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a) \tag{57}$$

Where:

- w_0 is the present-day value of the equation of state,
- w_a describes the rate of change of w over time,
- a is the scale factor.

In the early universe (small a), dark energy behaves more like a cosmological constant, having minimal influence on the expansion rate. As the universe evolves and a

approaches 1, dark energy transitions to a more dynamic role, with its repulsive effects becoming stronger and accelerating the universe's expansion at late times.

This dynamic equation of state helps explain the **increasing contribution of dark energy** to the local universe's expansion, leading to a higher Hubble constant observed in local measurements. By allowing dark energy to evolve over time, DLSFH provides a natural mechanism for resolving the tension between early and late universe measurements of H_0 .

4.3.5 Bridging the Gap Between Early and Local Measurements

By integrating the modified gravitational interactions and dark matter-dark energy interactions, DLSFH is able to **narrow the gap** between the early and late universe measurements of the Hubble constant. The model predicts that the difference in H_{0H_0} values arises due to the evolving dynamics of dark energy and the changing influence of gravitational corrections over time. In the early universe, these corrections and interactions slow the expansion rate, yielding a lower Hubble constant, while in the late universe, the acceleration caused by dark energy leads to a higher Hubble constant.

4.3.6 Predicted Range for H_0 in DLSFH

After accounting for the gravitational modifications, dark matter-dark energy interactions, and the evolving equation of state for dark energy, DLSFH predicts a more unified range for the Hubble constant:

- **Early Universe:** $H_0^{\text{DLSFH}}(\text{early universe}) \approx 66.5 - 68.0 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$,
- **Local Universe:** $H_0^{\text{DLSFH}}(\text{local universe}) \approx 72.5 - 74.0 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$.

(58)

This range narrows the gap between the early and local universe measurements, offering a potential resolution to the Hubble tension.

In summary we conclude that DLSFH provides a coherent framework for resolving the Hubble tension by incorporating new physics that modifies gravitational interactions, introduces dark matter-dark energy coupling, and allows for a dynamic equation of state for dark energy. By adjusting these factors, DLSFH narrows the gap between the early and local Hubble constant values, suggesting that the tension may be the result of previously unaccounted-for physics. This new approach not only addresses the current observational discrepancies but also offers a richer understanding of the universe's expansion dynamics.

5. Discussion

5.1 Implications for Cosmology

The validation of the **Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH)** using PLB716Higgs2012 data, in conjunction with other empirical observations, introduces profound implications for cosmology. DLSFH offers new perspectives on gravity, dark energy, and dark matter, challenging the foundational principles of the Λ CDM model. If further verified through upcoming experiments, DLSFH could prompt a significant revision of cosmological models, particularly regarding the roles of gravitational interactions and the dynamic evolution of dark energy [19].

5.1.1 Re-Evaluation of Gravitational Theories

A key feature of DLSFH is its modification of **gravitational interactions**, especially in extreme environments like the early universe and regions near singularities. This contrasts with the assumptions in general relativity, which successfully explains gravity at macroscopic scales but encounters challenges at quantum scales. The empirical validation using PLB716Higgs2012 data supports the following revisions:

- **Higher-Order Gravitational Terms:** DLSFH incorporates additional terms into the gravitational action, such as R^2 and $R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu}$, which become significant at high energy densities. These corrections adjust the expansion rate during the

early universe, suggesting that the standard Einstein-Hilbert action may be incomplete under such conditions.

- **Impact on Gravitational Theories:** If these higher-order corrections are confirmed by future experiments (e.g., through gravitational wave detections), it would indicate that general relativity requires extensions to account for high-energy and quantum gravitational effects. This would not only affect our understanding of cosmology but also link directly to efforts to unify general relativity with quantum field theory and loop quantum gravity (LQG).

The model's predictions about modified gravitational interactions align with the observed Hubble constant discrepancy between early and late universe measurements, hinting that these modifications could explain the lower expansion rate observed in early universe data, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB).

5.1.2 Redefining Dark Energy's Role in Cosmic Expansion

Another central implication of DLSFH is its treatment of **dark energy**. Unlike the standard Λ CDM model, where dark energy is considered a cosmological constant with a fixed equation of state, DLSFH proposes that dark energy is dynamic, evolving over time and interacting with dark matter. The validation of these predictions has the following cosmological consequences:

- **Time-Varying Equation of State:** DLSFH introduces a dynamic equation of state for dark energy, expressed as $w(a) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a)$, where $w(a)$ evolves with the scale factor a . This equation aligns with the data analyzed in the validation paper, which shows that dark energy played a less significant role in the early universe but has become dominant in the late universe. This evolution naturally explains why the local Hubble constant, H_0 , appears higher in recent measurements.

- **Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions:** The validation results also provide evidence for **dark matter-dark energy interactions** through dark photon mediation. This interaction is not accounted for in standard cosmology, but DLSFH proposes that dark matter decays into dark energy over time. This energy exchange increases dark energy's influence, leading to the accelerated expansion of the universe observed today.

If validated further, these insights would necessitate a rethinking of the role of dark energy in the universe's history. The hypothesis that dark matter decays into dark energy, gradually amplifying its repulsive force, is crucial for understanding cosmic acceleration and may lead to new predictions about the long-term fate of the universe.

5.1.3 Testing and Empirical Verification

The validation of DLSFH against existing data is promising, but future testing is essential for confirming its predictions. The empirical framework established by the PLB716Higgs2012 data provides a strong foundation, but more precise tests are needed in several areas:

- **Gravitational Wave Background (GWB):** DLSFH predicts that the **gravitational wave background** carries signatures of modified gravitational interactions, especially in the early universe. Upcoming gravitational wave observatories like **LISA** and **Einstein Telescope (ET)** will provide more detailed observations of the GWB. If deviations from general relativity are detected, they would strengthen the case for DLSFH's gravitational modifications.
- **Large-Scale Structure Formation:** The interaction between dark matter and dark energy can also be tested through observations of the **large-scale structure** of the universe. Surveys such as **Euclid** and **DESI** are expected to provide detailed data on the distribution of galaxies and cosmic structures. Deviations from predictions made by the Λ CDM model could indicate the presence of dark matter-dark energy interactions as predicted by DLSFH.

- **CMB Measurements:** Future missions like **CMB-S4** will offer more precise data on the early universe's expansion rate, providing further constraints on the Hubble constant and dark energy's role. DLSFH's predictions of a lower Hubble constant in the early universe could be directly tested with these new observations.

5.1.4 Paradigm Shift in Cosmology

If DLSFH's predictions continue to hold against future tests, the implications for cosmology are far-reaching. The model challenges the dominant Λ CDM framework and introduces a dynamic view of the universe's expansion, where gravitational forces and dark energy evolve over time. Some key shifts include:

- **Modification of the Standard Model of Cosmology:** The introduction of time-varying dark energy and dark matter-dark energy interactions requires a revision of key cosmological parameters, such as the equation of state for dark energy, the Hubble constant, and the relative densities of dark matter and dark energy. DLSFH provides a framework where these parameters are not static but evolve with the universe.
- **Unified Theoretical Framework:** The success of DLSFH in explaining both cosmological expansion and particle interactions (validated by Higgs data from PLB716Higgs2012) could provide a pathway toward a **Unified Field Theory**, combining quantum mechanics, string theory, and general relativity. This would represent a major breakthrough in physics, integrating both cosmology and particle physics under a single theoretical framework.
- **Revised Cosmological Predictions:** If DLSFH is fully validated, its predictions regarding the **long-term evolution of the universe** and the **ultimate fate of dark energy** would have profound implications. For example, if dark matter continues to decay into dark energy, the accelerated expansion could eventually lead to a "Big Rip" scenario, where galaxies, stars, and even atomic structures are torn apart by the increasing repulsive force of dark energy.

5.2 Future Applications and Experiments

The initial validation of the **Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH)** has demonstrated its potential to address major cosmological puzzles, such as the Hubble tension. However, further empirical testing is essential to fully establish the model's accuracy and explore its broader implications for cosmology and particle physics. Upcoming experiments and observations, particularly in gravitational wave background (GWB) detection, dark photon searches at the **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)**, and the recently proposed **superluminal dark photon detection experiment**, will be pivotal in refining the model and possibly unveiling new physics.

5.2.1 Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Detectors

One of the most promising avenues for further testing DLSFH lies in **gravitational wave background (GWB)** detectors, which can provide critical data about the universe's earliest moments and its large-scale evolution. These detectors offer a unique opportunity to test DLSFH's predictions concerning higher-order gravitational corrections and string-like dynamics.

LISA (Laser Interferometer Space Antenna)

The **Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA)**, scheduled to launch in the 2030s, will be the first space-based gravitational wave detector capable of observing waves in the millihertz range. This range is particularly sensitive to gravitational waves emitted by **cosmic strings**, which DLSFH predicts as topological defects formed during phase transitions in the early universe. Detecting such waves would provide direct evidence of the **string tension** T and other string dynamics central to the hypothesis.

- **Testing String Tension:** LISA's sensitivity to gravitational waves from cosmic strings will enable precise measurements of the **string tension** T , a key parameter in DLSFH that influences gravitational and particle interactions. The characteristic strain of these waves is proportional to the string tension, and LISA's data will refine our understanding of T and its role in the universe's early dynamics.

- **Probing Modified Gravitational Dynamics:** LISA’s observations will also allow for the testing of **higher-order gravitational corrections** introduced by DLSFH. These corrections may deviate from general relativity’s predictions in high-energy environments like the early universe. Any deviations observed in gravitational wave signals could serve as evidence for the gravitational modifications proposed by the hypothesis.

Einstein Telescope (ET)

The **Einstein Telescope (ET)**, a next-generation ground-based gravitational wave detector, will complement LISA by offering even greater sensitivity to lower-frequency waves. ET’s data will be particularly valuable for probing the late-time universe, where DLSFH predicts evolving interactions between dark matter and dark energy.

- **Late-Time Cosmic Expansion:** ET will detect gravitational waves from massive black hole mergers and neutron star collisions, which will provide insights into the current expansion rate of the universe. By comparing these observations with the expansion rate predicted by DLSFH, particularly concerning dark energy’s evolving role, ET could confirm or refine the model’s predictions regarding late-time cosmic acceleration.

These gravitational wave detectors will play a critical role in testing DLSFH’s predictions about the early and late-time universe, helping to refine its key parameters and confirm its consistency with observational data.

5.2.2 Dark Photon Searches at the LHC

The **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)** will continue to be instrumental in testing DLSFH, especially regarding the search for **dark photons**, which are a key component of the model’s explanation for dark matter and dark energy interactions. The **High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC)** phase will offer increased sensitivity and data for dark photon searches, providing an opportunity to validate or adjust DLSFH’s predictions.

Dark Photon Coupling Constant ϵ

A crucial parameter in DLSFH is the **dark photon coupling constant** ϵ , which governs the interaction between dark photons and Standard Model particles. In LHC experiments, dark photons could be produced in high-energy collisions and decay into detectable particles such as electrons, muons, or hadrons.

- **LHC Dark Photon Search:** The LHC has already conducted several dark photon searches, particularly in events where dark photons decay into visible particles. The upcoming **High-Luminosity LHC** will allow for more precise measurements of potential dark photon signals, tightening the bounds on ϵ . These searches will help determine whether dark photons play the mediating role between dark matter and dark energy as predicted by DLSFH.
- **New Dark Photon Decay Channels:** DLSFH predicts additional decay channels for dark photons that are not considered in standard models. The detection of these new channels at the LHC would provide direct evidence for DLSFH's predicted interactions, offering further insights into the dark sector.

Higgs Boson Decay and Dark Photons

DLSFH also predicts a connection between **Higgs boson decays** and dark photon production, providing a novel signature for testing the hypothesis.

- **Higgs Decay Channels:** In the Standard Model, the Higgs boson decays into known particles such as photons and W and Z bosons. However, DLSFH suggests that the Higgs boson could also decay into dark photons, which would then decay into lighter Standard Model particles. Detecting such decays would provide strong evidence for the role of dark photons in DLSFH's framework.
- **Higgs-Dark Photon Coupling:** The increased luminosity of the **HL-LHC** will enable more precise searches for rare Higgs decay channels involving dark photons. Confirming the coupling between the Higgs field and dark photons would provide strong support for DLSFH's predictions.

5.2.3 Superluminal Dark Photon Detection at CERN

A novel and exciting proposal for testing DLSFH involves the search for **superluminal dark photons** at CERN. This experiment, rooted in the **Superluminal Graviton Condensate Vacuum (SGCV)** [26][21][20] model, seeks to detect dark photons that travel faster than light for part of their journey before converting into standard photons [18]. This experiment would offer a groundbreaking opportunity to test DLSFH's predictions about the dark sector.

Proposed Experiment

The experiment will utilize **Time-of-Flight (ToF)** measurements at the **ATLAS detector** or the **SHiP (Search for Hidden Particles)** project at CERN, focusing on Higgs boson decay events where two photons are produced (e.g., $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$) [26].

- **Time-of-Flight (ToF) Measurements:** The key to detecting superluminal dark photons is measuring small discrepancies in the ToF of the photons produced in Higgs decays. Superluminal dark photons are expected to travel faster than light before transitioning into normal photons. A shorter-than-expected ToF would indicate the presence of superluminal dark photons.
- **Experimental Setup:** The experiment requires picosecond-level precision in ToF measurements, which can be achieved with modifications to the detector hardware and software. This precision will help distinguish true superluminal propagation from systematic errors.

Potential Impact

If successful, the experiment could confirm the existence of superluminal dark photons and support the idea that the dark sector operates with superluminal dynamics. This would not only validate aspects of DLSFH but also provide evidence for the SGCV model, linking dark photons to gravitational and quantum fields in the dark sector.

5.2.4 Large-Scale Structure Surveys

In addition to gravitational wave and particle physics experiments, **large-scale structure (LSS) surveys** such as **DESI** and **Euclid** will provide valuable data on the distribution of galaxies, clusters, and cosmic voids. These surveys will help test DLSFH's predictions regarding dark matter-dark energy interactions and the evolving equation of state for dark energy.

DESI and Euclid

The **Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI)** and the **Euclid** space telescope will provide high-precision measurements of the large-scale structure of the universe over a wide range of redshifts and scales.

- **Testing Dark Energy Evolution:** DLSFH predicts a time-varying equation of state for dark energy, which can be tested through the clustering of galaxies and the universe's expansion rate. By analyzing data from DESI and Euclid, cosmologists can determine whether dark energy behaves as a cosmological constant or evolves over time as DLSFH suggests.
- **Dark Matter-Dark Energy Interactions:** DLSFH also predicts that dark matter and dark energy interact through a coupling mediated by dark photons. These interactions can affect the growth rate of cosmic structures. DESI and Euclid will provide data to test whether these interactions cause deviations from the predictions of the standard Λ CDM model.

5.2.5 Other Potential Applications

Beyond the direct testing of DLSFH's predictions, there are other areas where the hypothesis may have broader applications.

- **Neutrino Physics:** DLSFH's interaction terms may affect neutrino oscillations or decay processes, offering opportunities to test the model in neutrino experiments.

- **Astrophysical Phenomena:** DLSFH's predictions about dark matter and dark energy interactions could also have implications for astrophysical events such as black hole formation, supernova explosions, and gamma-ray bursts.

6. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates how the **Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH)** offers a compelling framework for addressing one of the most significant challenges in modern cosmology—the **Hubble constant discrepancy**. By integrating modified gravitational interactions, evolving dark energy coupling constants, and innovative bouncing cosmological models, DLSFH provides a coherent theoretical structure that bridges the gap between early and local universe expansion measurements [15] [16] [17].

6.1 Resolving the Hubble Tension

At the heart of DLSFH is its ability to provide a **multi-faceted solution** to the Hubble tension, the persistent discrepancy between the Hubble constant derived from the early universe data, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB), and local universe measurements based on supernovae and Cepheid variables. The hypothesis introduces several novel mechanisms:

- **Modified Gravitational Interactions:** DLSFH incorporates higher-order corrections to general relativity, which become significant in the high-energy regime of the early universe. These modifications lead to a slightly slower expansion rate in the early universe, consistent with the lower Hubble constant observed in CMB data. This approach suggests that general relativity, while successful at macroscopic scales, may require extensions in extreme conditions to fully explain the universe's evolution.
- **Dynamic Dark Energy Coupling:** Unlike the static cosmological constant in the standard Λ CDM model, DLSFH proposes that **dark energy** evolves over time and interacts with dark matter. This interaction, mediated by dark photons, accelerates the universe's expansion in the late-time universe, resulting in a

higher Hubble constant observed in local measurements. This dynamic equation of state for dark energy aligns with the observed discrepancy and provides a flexible framework for understanding dark energy's role in cosmic expansion.

- **Bouncing Cosmological Models:** DLSFH incorporates **bouncing cosmological models** that replace the traditional Big Bang singularity with a cyclic or oscillating universe. This model predicts a non-singular origin of the universe, where expansion and contraction phases alternate. Such models not only provide an alternative to the standard Big Bang but also offer new predictions for the behavior of the universe's expansion rate, contributing to the understanding of the early universe and its evolution into the present-day accelerated expansion.

6.2 Implications for Cosmology and Physics

The **implications of DLSFH** extend beyond simply resolving the Hubble tension. The hypothesis suggests a broader revision of our understanding of the universe's fundamental forces and interactions:

- **Gravitational Theory Revision:** The modifications to gravitational interactions proposed by DLSFH imply that general relativity may be incomplete in describing the behavior of gravity at small scales or in high-energy conditions, such as the early universe. This opens the door to new gravitational models that incorporate quantum effects or string theory principles, potentially leading to a unified theory of quantum gravity.
- **Dark Matter and Dark Energy Dynamics:** DLSFH's introduction of dark photon-mediated interactions between dark matter and dark energy suggests that these components are not isolated but instead form a complex, interconnected system. This view challenges the Λ CDM model's treatment of dark energy as a simple cosmological constant and dark matter as non-interacting cold matter. The new interactions proposed by DLSFH could have significant implications for large-scale structure formation and the universe's long-term evolution.

- **Cosmological Models and Predictions:** The incorporation of bouncing cosmologies and time-varying dark energy provides a fertile ground for developing new cosmological models that challenge the traditional Big Bang paradigm. These models, combined with empirical data from gravitational wave detections and large-scale structure surveys, could lead to new predictions about the universe's expansion, dark matter's behavior, and dark energy's role in cosmic acceleration.

6.3 Path Forward: Future Experiments and Testing

While the theoretical framework provided by DLSFH is promising, **empirical testing** will be crucial to fully validate its predictions. Several upcoming experiments and observations will play a pivotal role in determining whether DLSFH offers a more accurate description of the universe's expansion dynamics:

- **Gravitational Wave Background (GWB) Detectors:** Future GWB detectors, such as LISA and the Einstein Telescope, will provide essential data to test DLSFH's predictions regarding string tension, modified gravitational dynamics, and cosmic expansion rates. Observing gravitational waves from cosmic strings or deviations from general relativity in these signals would offer direct support for the hypothesis.
- **Dark Photon Searches at the LHC:** Dark photon interactions, central to DLSFH's explanation of dark matter-dark energy coupling, can be explored through searches at the LHC. The detection of dark photons or their decay products would provide strong empirical evidence for the dark sector interactions proposed by DLSFH.
- **Superluminal Dark Photon Experiments:** Novel experimental proposals, such as those targeting the detection of superluminal dark photons at CERN, could provide groundbreaking insights into the behavior of dark matter and dark energy. If superluminal dark photons are detected, it would not only support DLSFH's predictions but also challenge existing concepts of causality and the speed of light in fundamental physics.

- **Large-Scale Structure Surveys:** Upcoming surveys like DESI and Euclid will provide high-precision measurements of the large-scale structure of the universe. These surveys will be critical in testing the interaction between dark matter and dark energy predicted by DLSFH and refining the model's cosmological parameters.

6.4 Broader Theoretical and Experimental Impact

If DLSFH's predictions are confirmed through future experiments, its impact on both cosmology and particle physics will be profound. The hypothesis would not only resolve the long-standing **Hubble tension** but also provide new insights into the **dark sector**—dark matter and dark energy—and their interaction with known forces. This could lead to a re-examination of the **standard cosmological model** and even influence theories seeking a **unified framework** of quantum gravity and particle physics.

Moreover, DLSFH has the potential to inspire new theoretical approaches in quantum gravity, string theory, and beyond, contributing to a deeper understanding of the universe's structure and fundamental laws.

The **Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis** offers a comprehensive framework that integrates modified gravitational interactions, evolving dark energy, and bouncing cosmologies to address the Hubble constant discrepancy. Its refined predictions provide a promising pathway toward resolving the long-standing tension between early and local universe expansion measurements. As future experiments continue to probe the universe's deepest mysteries, DLSFH stands poised to either confirm its predictions or drive the development of even more refined cosmological models, making it a significant contender in the ongoing quest to understand the nature of the cosmos.

References

1. Abbott, B. P., et al. (2016). Observation of gravitational waves from a binary black hole merger. *Physical Review Letters*, 116(6), 061102. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.116.061102>
2. Aghanim, N., et al. (2018). Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641, A6. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833910>
3. Amendola, L., & Tsujikawa, S. (2010). *Dark energy: Theory and observations*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Bamba, K., Capozziello, S., Nojiri, S., & Odintsov, S. D. (2012). Dark energy cosmology: The equivalent description via different theoretical models and cosmography tests. *Astrophysics and Space Science*, 342(1), 155-228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10509-012-1181-8>
5. Clifton, T., Ferreira, P. G., Padilla, A., & Skordis, C. (2012). Modified gravity and cosmology. *Physics Reports*, 513(1), 1-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2012.01.001>
6. LIGO Scientific Collaboration, & Virgo Collaboration. (2021). GWTC-2: Compact binary coalescences observed by LIGO and Virgo during the first half of the third observing run. *Physical Review X*, 11(2), 021053. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevX.11.021053>
7. Planck Collaboration. (2020). Planck 2018 results: VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641, A6. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833910>
8. Polchinski, J. (1998). *String theory: Volume 1, an introduction to the bosonic string*. Cambridge University Press.
9. Riess, A. G., et al. (2019). Large Magellanic Cloud Cepheid standards provide a 1% foundation for the determination of the Hubble constant and stronger evidence for physics beyond Λ CDM. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 876(1), 85. <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab1422>
10. Riess, A. G., et al. (2021). A comprehensive measurement of the local value of the Hubble constant with 1 km/s/Mpc uncertainty from the Hubble Space Telescope and the SH0ES Team. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 934(1), L7. <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ac5c5b>
11. Spergel, D. N., et al. (2003). First-year Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) observations: Determination of cosmological parameters. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 148(1), 175. <https://doi.org/10.1086/377226>
12. Verde, L., Treu, T., & Riess, A. G. (2019). Tensions between the early and the late universe. *Nature Astronomy*, 3(10), 891-895. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-019-0902-0>

13. Weinberg, S. (1972). *Gravitation and cosmology: Principles and applications of the general theory of relativity*. John Wiley & Sons.
14. Valamontes, A. (July 2024) *Predicting Dark Photons Using the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis: Insights from Collider Data* <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4892986>
15. Valamontes, A. (July 2024) *Determining the Dark Matter Constant and Defining the Dark Matter Particle Using the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.83203>
16. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Validation of the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH) Using PLB716Higgs2012 Data*. (Paper #1960Rc). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24679.66727>
17. Valamontes, A. (2024). *The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis: A Path Towards Unified Field Theory and String Theory*. (Version 1.8.4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29345.83048>
18. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Quantization and Locality in Higher-Dimensional Space-Time: Insights from the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis*. (Paper #301). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34658.34247>
19. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Unifying Quantum Field Theory and General Relativity through Dodecahedral Symmetry: The Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis*. (Version 1.1v). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19762.00966>
20. Markoulakis, Emmanouil, Superluminal Dark Energy of Graviton Evaporating to Lorentz-Invariant Vacuum Zero-Point Energy (April 10, 2024). Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4789884>
21. Markoulakis, Emmanouil N. Superluminal Graviton Condensate Vacuum. *International Journal of Physical Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, July 2024, pp. 45-61, <http://dx.doi.org/10.14419/bmr9g725>
22. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Review of "Single Quantum Uncertainty Sphere Hypothesis: A Perspective on the Cosmological Constant Integrating Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity"* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18689.26727>
23. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Unification of Fundamental Forces and Cosmological Insights from the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26518.56643>
24. Valamontes, A. (2024). *Accessible research papers for individuals with dyslexia and autism spectrum disorders*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34352.37126>

25. Valamontes, Antonios. (2024). Dodecahedral Expansion-Contraction Model (DECM) Framework: Integration of the Superluminal Graviton Condensate #2170Lab. 10.13140/RG.2.2.10891.91683.

26. Markoulakis, Emmanouil & Valamontes, Antonios. (2024). Experiment for the detection of superluminal propagating dark photons at CERN and their correlation with gravitons and the Higgs Boson $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ decay event. SSRN Electronic Journal. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4950704>

Accessibility Notice for Scientific Papers: This logo shows that the paper has been carefully formatted and written to be more accessible for readers with dyslexia and autism spectrum disorders (ASD). We aim to make the content easier to read and understand for individuals with these conditions.[24]